

EVALUATION OF INITIAL AND FINAL SET TIMES AND HEAT OF HYDRATION OF GYPSUM PASTES, WITH THE INCORPORATION OF DIFFERENT RESIDUE CONTENTS OF STONE POWDER.

Antônio C.B. Filho, Federal da Paraíba University, BRAZIL, antoniofilho@cagepa.pb.gov.br
Normando P. Barboza, Federal University of Paraíba, BRAZIL, nperazzob@yahoo.com.br

ABSTRACT

This work studies the incorporation of stone powder residues in gypsum matrices and its influence on the initial and final set time. They are essential for the production processes. The behavior of commercial gypsum pastes was investigated with the substitution of stone powder in percentages ranging between 10% and 50%, and with water/gypsum ratios between 0.50 and 0.90, in relation to the pick-up times and the kinetics of the reactions. The results obtained show variation in the initial and final set times of the composites as well as in the kinetics of the reactions as the residue content increases.

KEYWORDS

Hydration heat, gypsum composite; set time.

INTRODUCTION

Increasingly, there is a growing evolution in modern society in the demand for construction materials, which leads us to question the use of these materials regarding environmental preservation. Given this reality there is a concern directly related to one of the main materials used in civil construction, the plaster, primarily with regard to its final destination, because it is a material that in contact with the environment, can become toxic, considering that its residues are composed of dihydrate calcium sulfate that in contact with oxygen and water oxidize becoming toxic. The solubilization of this material directly causes the contamination of the groundwater and the sulfurization of the soil (John; Cincotto, 2003).

Improper disposal of plaster in clandestine landfills or boot-offs can cause the components to be dissolving and make it flammable. It is noteworthy that humid environments, associated with aerobic conditions and the presence of sulfate-reducing bacteria, allow the dissociation of residue components into carbon dioxide, water and sulphide gas. The sulphide gas can paralyze the central nervous system, responsible for the control of breathing, which can cause asphyxia being also flammable, and at concentrations above 8ppm (parts per million) can cause intense irritation in the eyes and become potentially lethal at concentrations of 500ppm. In general, the effects of hydrogen sulphide poisoning are severe and, as a comparison effect, similar to the effects of carbon monoxide poisoning (Pandey and Malhotra, 1999). The incineration of gypsum can also produce sulphur dioxide (John; Cincotto, 2003).

According to Ahmed et al. (2011), during the three stages of gypsum use, production, construction, and demolition, about 15 million tons of waste of this material is generated annually worldwide. Therefore, the development of research aimed at reducing the disposal of these residues is extremely beneficial for the environment.

Considering that one of the major causes of gypsum waste during its application is caused by the short time between the initial set time and the end of the handle, and that only at this stage are produced

material losses, in the order of 35%, techniques and additions that provide a change of this property in the gypsum paste can cause a smaller waste of the material.

The pick time can be defined as that elapsed from the moment the hemidrate comes into contact with the crumpling water until its hardening (Baltar, 2009).

For Savi (2012), the moment when the crystallization of the paste begins is defined as the beginning of the handle (initial set time), whose time is measured from the moment of the binder's hydration; The end of handle (final set time) is defined as the final moment of hardening, when the product has acquired greater strength.

The hardening of the gypsum paste occurs by the hydration reaction, in a process in which heat detachment occurs (Munhoz & Renófió, 2006). After contact with the squeaking water, the paste has a limited time for use, shorter than other binders, such as cement. The determination of the start and end set times are important for industrial processes, because they allow quantifying the equipment and personnel needed to perform the tasks. From your knowledge, you can define the time for molding and deform components. The pick times are directly influenced by the kinetics of hydration reactions that present different behaviors in commercial gypsum pastes and in the gypsum paste with additions.

The plaster handle times can be increased or reduced to suit the logistics needs of its use. They can be increased with the increase of calcination temperature and granulometry (Bauer, 2001) and also with the increase in the amount of snorewater (Petrucci, 1998). They can be reduced by increasing the crushing energy (Magnan, 1973 apud Antunes, 1999) and by increasing the mixing time (Ribeiro, 2006). Additive stake controllers also interfere with the speed of the reaction.

Of the items mentioned, water gypson ratio (w/g) is attributed to greater responsibility in the influence of hydration reactions of the gypsum. The higher the amount of water, the longer the time required for the formation of dihydrate crystals and precipitation (onset of handle), i.e., results in an increase in induction period (Antunes; John, 2000).

Another factor of great relevance, whose knowledge is widely used in the techniques of application of coating in gypsum paste, is the increase of energy in the mixture. The energy applied in the mixture increases the dispersion of the powder in the skimming water and, consequently, there is the formation of a larger amount of crystallization nuclei, accelerating the hydration process. The study conducted by Blaine (1997) is an example of scientific basis of the procedures commonly adopted in the work, where gypsum applicators, at first, put only 50% of the volume of gypsum in the container, in order to delay the hydration.

The presence of impurities, which are foreign elements to the mixture of gypsum paste, is another factor that accelerates the set time of the pastes; aggregates, such as dihydrate itself or grains of sand, act as crystallization nuclei, which causes the acceleration of hydration reactions (Antunes; John, 2000).

The hydration mechanism can be explained by calorimetry. Being the hydration heat curve of a gypsum paste presented in three stages (Antunes; John, 1999), in which, in the first stage, a small hydration occurs, followed by the induction period. This step is completed when the temperature elevation rate exceeds 0.1°C/min, characterizing the initial set time. The second stage is characterized by the rapid rise in temperature, that is, hydration is evolving faster. The third stage is the instant in which the reaction reaches the maximum temperature that corresponds to the completion of hydration, the final set time.

This curve can be obtained using an easy-to-make pseudoadiabatic calorimeter and, through it, it is possible to obtain the useful time of gypsum pastes ranging on average from around 20 min to 30 min, and the consistency range is adequate for its use. This consistency range can also be determined for the gypsum mortar (paste + residue), helping to reduce the waste of the material on the construction site

itself, since the execution of the coating generates a huge volume of waste, due to its less than conventional hardening speed.

Given the above, this work aims to present an environmentally correct solution that would be the use of stone powder in gypsum pastes for the manufacture of blocks for the construction of masonry. This solution is based on the encapsulation of stone powder from the crushing of granite rocks in the gypsum paste, giving rise to a composite material. For this purpose, the initial and final set time was studied using the Vicat's apparatus and using a pseudoadiabatic calorimeter.

The incorporation content of stone powder varied between 0% and 50% in relation to gypsum mass. Gypsum water (w/g) ratios between 0.5 and 0.9 were used in order to analyze which composition offers the most appropriate performance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The materials that were the object of study of this work were water, commercial gypsum and stone powder.

Water

All water used for the preparation of the pastes, cleaning of equipment, devices or other purposes was provided by the local concessionaire (CAGEPA), considered drinking and proper for use in construction activities.

Gypsum

The gypsum used in the experimental tests was commercial gypsum, according to the specific conditions presented in Brazilian standard NBR 13867 (ABNT, 1997). According to the information of the supplier company, it is the most used in the city of Cajazeiras – PB, and surroundings.

Stone powder

The stone powder was acquired in the crusher CAJABRITA located also in the city of Cajazeiras - PB. After its acquisition, all the material used in the research was sieved in the sieve of no. 4.8 using only the passing material in this sieve.

Methods

ABNT NBR 12128 (ABNT, 1991) defines the initial set time as being the time elapsed from the moment the gypsum met the water, until the moment that the needle of the Vicat's apparatus no longer penetrates the bottom of the paste, that is, 1 mm above the base.

The final set time is the time elapsed from the memento in which the gypsum came into contact with water, until the moment when the needle of Vicat's apparatus no longer leaves an impression on the surface of the paste.

The initial set time determines the period that a worker must handle the material. The final set time, on the other hand, corresponds to time when the paste is considered hardened.

The tests, using the Vicat's apparatus, were performed according to the methods described in Brazilian standard NBR 12128:1991 (MB-3469).

For the calorimeter tests, which is an alternative method, the methodology adopted by Antunes (1999 apud Savi, 2012) was followed..

Experimental planning

In a first stage, the plaster pastes called control or reference were prepared, without any stone powder. The reference pastes were prepared with w/g ratio 0.5, 0.6, 0.7 0.8 and 0.9. After this stage, the experimental plan included the execution in the laboratory of mixtures with incorporations of 10%,

20%, 30%, 40% and 50% of stone powder in place of the gypsum mass for each w/g ratio, totaling 30 (thirty) samples.

Mixture

The mixture was carried out at room temperature of approximately 30°C. The water was put in a plastic container and the gypsum sprayed in the water for a period of 1 minute. Then the paste was mixed for 1 minute and then put to rest for 2 minutes. After the rest period, the paste was placed in plastic cups for calorimetry testing or in the Vicat's apparatus.

In mixtures with w/g = 0.5 with substitution percentages of 40 % and 50% it was not possible to mold the specimens since the mixtures did not acquire plasticity.

Test with Vicat's appliance

The Vicat's apparatus consists of a support that supports a movable rod with 300 ± 0.5 g and which has at its end a removable needle of nominal cross section of 1 mm^2 , with a length of 50 mm and $\pm$ diameter of 1.13 ± 0.02 mm. The rod can be kept suspended at the desired height by means of a screw. The device also has an adjustable indicator, which moves on a scale graduated in millimeters and which is attached to the support and which serves to measure the height of the needle tip to the surface of the glass. Complements the assembly a container with cone trunk shape and a glass plate that serves as support for the container.

Hydration heat

The test also indicates the time of initial and final set time by analyzing the hydration heat curves as a function of time, generated by temperature variation during the hydration reactions of the gypsum (which releases energy). The parameter adopted to determine the initial set time is when the thermal gradient exceeded $0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, and the final set time was the moment when the maximum temperature was reached, evidenced by the interruption of the temperature elevation.

A pseudoadiabatic calorimeter proposed by Murat and Jeandot (1973) and a stopwatch (Figure 1) were used.

Figure 1: Pseudoadiabatic calorimeter

The mixing procedure was the same as adopted in the set time test. After mixing, the pastes were placed in plastic cups, connected to the thermometer. Subsequently, they were inserted into EPS containers filled with thermally insulating material, aiming at the non-interference of the external temperature. The temperature was measured every two minutes, passing through its sudden temperature elevation (apex of reactions), until the moment when the temperature increase was interrupted, being reached the maximum temperature.

PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Evaluation of the effect of replacing the stone powder at the beginning and end of the plaster pastes.

Table 1 shows the results of the effect of the different levels of stone powder replacement in the initial set time of the plaster pastes with w/g ratios ranging from 0.5 to 0.9.

Table 1: Initial Set Time Values

INITIAL SET TIMES – VICAT'S APPLIANCE					
w/g ratio					
Substitution Content	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,9
0%	00:07:42	00:10:22	00:16:49	00:22:01	00:55:54
10%	00:05:55	00:10:07	00:13:28	00:17:28	00:38:52
20%	00:04:35	00:09:35	00:11:17	00:13:09	00:27:07
30%	00:03:40	00:09:15	00:10:34	00:12:45	00:19:45
40%		00:08:24	00:10:00	00:12:01	00:17:41
50%		00:08:12	00:09:27	00:10:37	00:11:32

Figure 2 shows the graphic related to the Table 1.

Figure 2: Variation of the initial set time with w/g ratio and percentage of replacement of gypsum by stone powder

The results showed that the addition of stone powder regardless of the w/g ratio influenced reducing the initial set time. A decrease in the plasticity of the material was also observed. This is due to the fact that dihydrate crystals grow from crystallization gems or nuclei. The amount of nuclei present in the solution directly influences the growth rate of the microstructure, when there are many nuclei the growth is fast which accelerates the hardening of the paste and consequently the initial set time, when there are few nuclei the growth is slower. Given this characteristic the grains of stone powder will act as

crystallization nuclei accelerating hydration reactions and consequently the larger the amount of these grains the shorter the start time of the handle.

It can be observed that the influence of the addition of stone powder in the reduction of the start time of handle is particularly relevant in mixtures with higher water/gypsum ratios. In these mixtures this occurs due to the fact that with the greatest amount of water the crystallization nuclei are further away from each other causing the dihydrate crystals originating from these nuclei to take longer to intertwine to give consistency to the paste. The addition of stone powder in the pastes with this characteristic, even in a small amount, brings the crystallization nuclei closer to allowing the fastest interlacing, which in percentage terms is more significant than in raisins with low water/gypsum ratio, since these pastes already naturally have nearest crystallization nuclei.

This phenomenon is clearly observed when in the mixture with water/gypsum ratio 0.9 without any addition that had its onset of handle in 55min and 54s. When compared to the trait with the same ratio with an increment of only 10% of stone powder, this period was changed to 38min and 52s, a decrease of 30.47% in the pick-up time. The trait with respect to $w/g = 0.5$ without substitution had its onset of handle in 7 min and 42 s and with the increase of the same 10% replacement had this value changed to 5 min and 55 s, which represents a decrease of only 10.40%.

It is also observed that for all the mixtures studied, the increase in the increase in the replacement of gypsum by stone powder is producing a gradual flattening of the initial set time, a fact explained by three different aspects. The first refers to the saturation of the paste by the so-called crystallization nuclei. As the number of these nuclei increases exponentially with the replacement content, at some point these nuclei will be so close that the influence of each one on the formation of dihydrate crystals is less significant. The second refers to the fact that as in this study the stone powder enters as partial replacement of the plaster, keeping constant the water/gypsum ratio there is consequently a reduction in the water/dry materials ratio causing less water present in the mixture, consequently decreasing the hydration speed. The third factor is related to the fact that when replacing the gypsum by stone powder, the specific area of the mixture is significantly reduced, since the plaster is much more fine than the stone powder, thus having a smaller area in hydration which slows down the processes of the reactions.

This behavior becomes clear when one observes the mixture w/g 0.7 with 10% replacement that had its initial set time 19min and 48s and the one with w/g 0.7 with 50% replacement that had 12min and 49s. There is a decrease of only 35.27% in the initial set time even if the replacement increment has increased from 10% to 50%.

It was also observed that for all compositions studied when changing the replacement value from 20% to 40% there is practically no variation in the pastes initial set time. This observation becomes explicit when analyzing the trait with water/gypsum ratio 0.8 with 20% replacement that had its initial set time in 16min and 45s and the mix with $w/g = 0.8$ with 40% that had 16 min and 08 s. The variation in these two folders was only 3.30%.

Table 2 presents the numerical data of the effect of the different levels of stone at the final set time of the composites.

Table 2: Final Set Time Values.

END-OF-HANDLE TIMES - VICAT APPLIANCE					
Factor (w/g)					
Substitution Content	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,9
0%	00:08:39	00:14:16	00:23:06	00:27:49	01:06:16
10%	00:07:45	00:13:55	00:19:48	00:21:19	00:55:30
20%	00:05:30	00:13:24	00:14:12	00:16:45	00:34:40
30%	00:04:39	00:12:26	00:14:00	00:16:23	00:24:50
40%		00:12:24	00:13:40	00:16:08	00:24:10
50%		00:11:32	00:12:49	00:13:18	00:17:17

Figure 3 shows the graphic related to Table 2.

Figure 3: Variation of final sent times with the w/g ratio and percentage of gypsum replacement by stone powder

When analyzing the data presented above, it can be seen that the effect of stone powder produces in the pastes effect similar to those observed at the initial set time.

A relevant data that was verified was the fact that for the mix with w/g of 0.7 and 0% of substitution the initial set time occurred in 16 min and 49 s and the end of the handle in 23 min and 9 s which results in a time interval elapsed between the start and the end of the handle of 6 min and 17 s. The mix with w/g = 0.7 and 40% substitution that hat initial set time in 10min and final set time in 13min and 10s, the time interval was 3min and 40s, which proves that the addition of 40% of stone powder in the mixture causes a reduction of 58.35% in the time elapsed between the initial and final set time. This decrease was observed in all mixtures analyzed.

Evaluation of the effect of stone powder substitution on the thermodynamics of gypsum paste reactions.

In all mixtures, a typical behavior of calorimetry curves in gypsum pastes was identified. The obtained graphs are displayed in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Calorimetric curves with different replacement levels

Analyzing Figure 5, there is a reduction in the induction period of the pastes with the incorporation of stone powder, when compared to the reference pastes, indicating an increase in the speed of the hydration reaction. This phenomenon occurs because the grains of stone powder act as a crystallization nucleus in the pastes.

Similar behaviors are identified, however the stage 2 of the curves (acceleration stage and initial set time) the curves are shown with a lower angle of inclination in the mixtures with residue. This is justified, because the residue for the same reason that it reduces the induction period forming crystallization nuclei causes the acceleration of reactions.

It was observed that the increase in the residue content did not significantly alter the initial and final times set time, besides promoting a decrease in the peak of the maximum temperature.

Table 3 shows the results of maximum temperature and time to reach it for commercial gypsum pastes, and gypsum with the addition of stone powder. The time to reach the maximum temperature represents the time it takes the plaster to reach its hardened state.

Table 3: Maximum temperature and time to reached it

Factor (w/g)	Substitution Content	Maximum Temperature	Time to reach it
0.9	0(%)	46.9°C	30min
	10(%)	45.3°C	26min
	20(%)	44.9°C	26min
	30(%)	44.5°C	24min
	40(%)	46.6°C	24min
	50(%)	43.3°C	24min
0.8	0(%)	47.1°C	28min
	10(%)	46.8°C	24min
	20(%)	48.3°C	22min
	30(%)	47.6°C	26min
	40(%)	43.9°C	26 min
	50(%)	43.4°C	24min
0.7	0(%)	49.7°C	26min
	10(%)	50.4°C	28min
	20(%)	45.9°C	26min
	30(%)	47.1°C	24min
	40(%)	46.8°C	22min
	50(%)	46.3°C	20min
0.6	0(%)	52.3°C	24min
	10(%)	51.3°C	24min
	20(%)	50.4°C	22min
	30(%)	50.0°C	22min
	40(%)	48.9°C	22min
	50(%)	46.2°C	16min
0.5	0(%)	56.9°C	20min
	10(%)	56.0°C	20min
	20(%)	54.8°C	22min
	30(%)	50.7°C	24min
	40(%)	47.5°C	24min
	50(%)	46.9°C	28min

Analyzing the mixtures with w/g = 0.9 it is noted that the addition of stone powder did not significantly alter the hardening times of the paste since when compared to the mixtures with 0% replacement that reached the maximum temperature in 30min and the mixture with 50% replacement that had its maximum temperature reached in 24 min. There was a decrease in this time of 20%. This contradicts the data obtained through Vicat's test, which found a sharper decrease in the useful time of use of the

pastes.

When verifying the data obtained in the mixtures with $w/g = 0.6$, it was noticed that with the increase of substitution there was a gradual decrease in the maximum hydration heat reached. This is due to the fact that part of the plaster, material responsible for exothermic reactions, was replaced by inert material that does not release heat, consequently decreasing the total heat released in the hydration process.

The observed behavior corroborates the trends identified in the previous analyses. The increase in the residue content caused a reduction in the initial and final set time, mainly compared to the reference paste.

CONCLUSIONS

The study highlights the conclusions:

- In all mixtures with the residue, it was observed that the presence of stone powder accelerates the hydration of the gypsum, indicating that the particles added to the solution constitute crystallization nuclei;
- The amount of water also influences the initial and final set time and has a direct growth relationship with the increase of the water/gypsum ratio;
- The consistency of the gypsum pastes decreases with the increase of the addition of stone powder worsening its workability, however, for replacements of up to 30% this decrease is not significant;
- The pastes with $w/g = 0.5$ and with substitution percentages higher than 30% presented a great acceleration in the hydration process showing the inefficiency of these mixes. The moldings became problematic due to the rapid hardening of the pastes, which led to the impossibility of carrying out the tests;
- For the use of stone powder in gypsum pastes, it should be considered that the reaction kinetics releases a smaller amount of heat than commercial gypsum pastes, and, the time required for the hardening process is also shorter;
- The use of inorganic additions, in this case, stone powder proved to be efficient in this research, which can probably contribute to the reduction of gypsum consume in plasters products and diminishing waste reducing impacts on the environment by reducing the disposal of this unused material due to the short working time.
- Considering all these aspects it can be concluded, based on the results obtained, that there is potential for the application of stone powder residue in the production of gypsum pastes, in substitution levels of up to 40%. However, some application should be associated with the use of handle retardant admixtures.

REFERENCES

AHMED, A.; UGAI, K.; KAMEI, T. Investigation of recycled gypsum in conjunction with waste plastic trays for ground improvement. *Construction and Building Materials*. v. 25, Jan. 2011, p. 208-217.

ANTUNES, R. P. N. Study of the influence of hydrated lime on gypsum pastes. Master's degree in Engineering dissertation from the Polytechnic School. Sao Paulo. 1999.

ANTUNES, R.P.N.; JOHN, V.M. The Useful Time Concept of Gypsum Pastes. São Paulo: Polytechnic School of the University of São Paulo, 2000. Technical bulletin.

BRAZILIAN ASSOCIATION OF TECHNICAL STANDARDS (ABNT). NBR 12128: Plaster for construction - Determination of the physical properties of the paste. Rio de Janeiro. 1991.

BRAZILIAN ASSOCIATION OF TECHNICAL STANDARDS (ABNT). NBR 13867: Internal coating of walls and ceilings with plaster paste - materials, preparation, application and finishing - procedure. Rio de Janeiro, 1997.

BALTAR, L.M. Influence of the Addition of Polysaccharides on the Physical Properties of Alpha Gypsum. Dissertation (Master in Mineral Engineering), Federal University of Pernambuco, Graduate Program in Mineral Engineering, Technology and Geoscience Center, Recife, 2009, cap. 2, pag. 7.

BAUER, L.A.F. Building Materials. Vol. 1, 5. Ed. Revised. LTC - Livros Técnicos e Científicos Editora S.A. (1979). 2001.

BLAINE, S. Accelerating the Hydration of Calcium Sulfate Hemihydrates Via High Energy Mixing. Materials and Structures, v. 30, p. 362-365, Jul. 1997.

JOHN, V.M.; CINCOTTO, M. A O. Alternatives For The Management of Gypsum Waste. University of São Paulo - Polytechnic School, p. 1–9, 2003.

MUNHOZ, F.C. and RENÓFIO, A. Use of Gypsum in Civil Construction and Adequacy for P+L. XIII SIMPEC. Bauru. 2006.

MURAT, M.; JEANDOT, G. Méthodes de Mésures et Interprétation des Effets Thermiques Associés à l'Hydratation des Sulfates de Calcium et des Plâtres Industriels. Rêvue de Matériaux de Construction. v. 680, p. 14-23, 1973.

PANDEY R. A., MALHOTRA, S. Desulfuritation of gaseous fuels with recovery of elemental sulfur: An overview critical reviews in environmental Science and Technology. 29(3), 292-268, 1999.

PETRUCCI, E. G. R. Building Materials, 11th ed. Globo Publishing House. Sao Paulo. 1998.

PINHEIRO, S. M.M. Recycled gypsum: evaluation of properties for use in components. Campinas, 2011. 330 p. Thesis (Doctorate) - Graduate Program of the Faculty of Civil - UNICAMP, 2011.

RIBEIRO, A.S. Production of recycled gypsum from waste from Civil Construction. 2006. 105 pg. Master's thesis in Urban Engineering. Graduate Program in Urban Engineering. Federal University of Paraíba. João Pessoa. March 2006.

SAVI, O. Production of Lining Plates with Gypsum Recycling. Dissertation (Master in Urban Engineering), State University of Maringá, Graduate Program in Urban Engineering, Maringá, 2012.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.